

Adaptive Approximate Computing with CGRAgen

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Abstract—Modern Edge applications are diverse and compute-intensive but can often afford constrained computational inaccuracy. Commonly denoted approximate computing, this paper explores the integration of inexact arithmetic units into Coarse-Grained Reconfigurable Array (CGRA) architectures with an associated, comprehensive framework for architecture modeling, hardware generation, and automated approximation, CGRAgen. A use case kernel from signal processing illustrates the functionality and potential of CGRAgen in design space explorations into CGRAs with integrated approximate computing techniques, highlighting the utility of making approximations reconfigurable.

Index Terms—Approximate computing, reconfigurable hardware, electronic design automation.

I. INTRODUCTION

EFFECTIVELY tackling the growing rate of data production in Internet of Things devices and their associated demands for connectivity requires distributing compute capacity across the network and along its Edge. Distributed devices often have constrained computational capabilities and energy availability but must deliver high performance in various applications. This difficult balance requires hardware acceleration and has recently motivated exploiting the error tolerance of the target applications through deliberate Approximate Computing (AxC). Approximation adds a third angle to the traditional time-energy trade-off spectrum: quality, whose constraints a computing device must adapt to at run-time [1].

Highly constrained Edge devices cannot accommodate several hardware accelerators or large programmable architectures. Rather, the integrated accelerator should be reconfigurable to achieve sufficient performance while maintaining adaptability and maximizing the available benefits of AxC [1]. Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) provide such features but incur high overheads from their bit-level granularity and need for hardware design prowess. Coarse-Grained Reconfigurable Arrays (CGRAs) mitigate these downsides with word-level reconfigurability and compiler-like tooling for programming [2]. When tightly coupled with a host processor, compute-heavy kernels can be offloaded to the CGRA to improve performance and energy efficiency.

Researching CGRAs requires a flexible modeling and mapping flow. Yet, despite an upwards publication trend, only a few works are associated with open-source software. Popular examples include CGRA-ME [3], Pillars [4], and OpenCGRA [5]. CGRA-ME is considered the academic standard

and was recently upgraded with several advanced architectural features. Most of these flows unfortunately suffer either from strict architectural models or too deep an integration of their Architecture Description Languages (ADLs) with the languages they are written in [6]. Moreover, despite prior work showing good results from integrating AxC into CGRAs [1], no existing flow supports such techniques. We aim to remediate this lack of tooling and motivate further research.

We contribute an integrated flow to model and map applications to generic CGRAs with inexact arithmetic, *CGRAgen*. Extending upon our prior work [6], *CGRAgen* is written in Scala and combines hardware generation features with automatic approximation of application kernels to match inexact arithmetic units in the target architecture. We provide a demonstration of its features in CGRA design space exploration, initial results from a signal processing use case, and a discussion of future development opportunities. *CGRAgen* is available in open source on GitHub.

This paper is structured as follows: Section II covers the architecture modeling and hardware generation components of *CGRAgen*, while Section III presents its mapping and approximation features. Section IV provides the signal processing use case experiment with *CGRAgen*. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and suggests directions for future research.

II. MODELING AND GENERATING HARDWARE

CGRAgen purposefully integrates a generic hardware modeling flow despite the potential difficulties it brings to the remaining tool components. This is motivated by the great architectural variance in CGRAs from the literature [2]. The flow comprises three stages: parsing, modeling, and generation, which form a natural pipeline from high-level architectural descriptions to either Modulo Resource Routing Graphs (MRRGs) for mapping or Verilog code for synthesis or simulation. We describe the three stages in this section and provide an example of their use in Section IV.

Some recent CGRAs integrate predication and elastic scheduling for improved flexibility. *CGRAgen* does not support such features yet. Rather, we aim to enable an initial design space exploration into adaptive AxC. Therefore, we consider only CGRAs whose Processing Elements (PEs) operate in lockstep. This decision simplifies tool development but constrains the architectures and applications it can handle.

A. Parsing

CGRAgen's hardware modeling flow takes as input a description of a CGRA written in its ADL, which is based on XML and inspired by CGRA-ME [3]. A collection of hardware primitives with pre-defined functionality is at the core of the

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Fig. 1: Illustrative block diagrams of the adaptive inexact OFLOCA-style adder (left) and radix-2 multiplier (right) supported by CGRagen. By default, the units are configured with three approximation modes for the least-significant half of their operands.

ADL. A CGRA description comprises constant definitions, module templates, and one architecture that delineates the structural patterns of the CGRA. The module templates serve to compound primitives and, possibly, other module instances into, e.g., PEs. The associated parser is implemented with the remaining tool elements using the `scala.xml` package, avoiding third-party dependencies and simplifying extensions.

B. Modeling

CGRagen relies on object-oriented programming to expand parsed architectures into hierarchies of abstract module classes. The primitives – Arithmetic Logic Units (ALUs), constant units, multiplexers, registers, register files, and input/output units – are at the bottom of this hierarchy, with all other modules, including the CGRA itself, compounding and connecting any number of sub-modules. We do not integrate memory primitives as the lack of elastic scheduling would require them to have an unreasonable single-cycle read/write access latency *or* their associated load/store units to synchronize on data availability to enable the CGRA data path. Memories and load/store units may be included in wrappers around the CGRA instead. The hierarchical intermediate representation is not enforced by the ADL but lets us minimize redundant code.

C. Generation

Rather than relying on hand-written hardware description language generation, CGRagen (like Pillars [4]) uses Chisel to generate Verilog code [7]. The modeled CGRAs are converted into Chisel modules bottom-up based on pre-defined descriptions of the primitives. This process is complicated by the input/output unit primitives, which are needed for mapping operations for explicit handling of input/output data to/from the CGRA but converted to mere ports in hardware, as the IO of any compound module may depend on the contents of its sub-modules. This clashes with traditional declarative design in Chisel and Scala’s parent class first construction order. We avoid these issues by lazily evaluating module IO and wrapping hardware construction in an inherited method [6].

We construct the top-level CGRA module similarly but use Chisel’s hierarchy features to enforce deduplication, i.e., the declaration and reuse of identical sub-modules. The primitives that require configuration bits have these bits collected in registers in their top-most encapsulating sub-module. In anticipation of needing an external controller, CGRagen integrates

two styles for these registers: parallel-load and serial. The latter lets CGRA sub-modules be chained, simplifying control at the expense of increased reconfiguration time. The former is most frequently applied in the literature [1], [8].

D. Integration of AxC

CGRagen currently only supports approximation with inexact arithmetic, specifically adders and multipliers. Inspired by X-CGRA [1], we consider reconfigurable arithmetic units to keep the resource overheads of their integration low and permit intermittent exact execution. Accordingly, we propose novel adaptations of recent inexact adder and multiplier designs, illustrated in Fig. 1. The adder is inspired by the optimized feedback lower-part constant-OR adder (OFLOCA). It uses constant ones or OR gates in its least significant part [9]. The multiplier implements dynamic truncation on some least significant columns in a radix-2 partial product tree with a simple error mitigation strategy. The adder and multiplier are integrated with CGRagen based on reference implementations from our open source *approx* library available on GitHub.

The designs are parameterized by how many least-significant bits or partial product columns to approximate, and how many approximation modes to support. The number of approximated bits or partial product columns grows with the approximation mode index and affects the magnitude and frequency of errors. We let mode 0 denote exact operation and assign the parameters default values of half the operand bit-width and three modes to balance usefulness and reconfiguration costs. Users can alter these values through CGRagen’s configuration file, which provides default values for all tool parameters. We permit integration of these designs globally (with a configuration flag) and partially (with ADL attributes).

III. MAPPING AND APPROXIMATING KERNELS

Most recent CGRA exploration tools include engines for mapping application kernels on their target architectures [3]–[5]. Such kernels are expressed as Data Flow Graphs (DFGs) with operations represented by nodes and data dependencies represented by directed edges. Accordingly, CGRagen operates on DFGs, whose operations are constrained to those supported by its hardware flow (and any target CGRA).

A. Parsing and Modeling

The application modeling flow in CGRAgen takes as input DFGs described in a subset of the DOT language. This language is sufficiently simple to avoid third-party dependencies again and parse with a `RegexParser` from the `scala.util.parsing.combinators` package. We permit multiple declarations of nodes but require that each node defines exactly one `opcode` attribute, which captures its operation. Similarly, we require that each edge specifies an `operand` attribute, which captures its (unique) arithmetic position in the sink operation. For instance, an addition node should be the sink of two edges with `operand` attributes 0 and 1. For automated approximation, we require that all approximable output nodes are assigned an `approx` attribute whose value constrains the relative error distance variance.

B. Optional Passes

By default, CGRAgen leaves all DFGs output by the parser that are not marked with `approx` attributes untouched before mapping. However, the tool provides a collection of passes to change or supplement the DFGs according to user specifications in anticipation of improving mapping feasibility or in preparation for automated approximation. All these passes take a DFG and a CGRA as arguments, as some require knowledge about the target architecture. We assign all passes two lists of pre- and post-requisite passes and apply them in topologically sorted order. The currently supported passes with names indicating their functionality are:

- `PropagateConstPass`
- `RemoveDeadPass`
- `MaxFanoutPass`
- `ReplicateConstPass`
- `MarkApproximablePass`
- `EstimateErrorsPass`

The latter two passes are required to mark approximable arithmetic operations and estimate the errors produced by the inexact arithmetic units in the target CGRA through simulation. To avoid costly and unnecessary re-simulations, we cache these error characteristics between runs.

C. Mapping Procedure

Unlike CGRA-ME [3] and X-CGRA [1], CGRAgen does not integrate a mapping engine based on integer linear programming. Such algorithms have benefits in mapping quality and early infeasibility detection but tend to suffer from high compilation time. Instead, we follow the essence of CGRAgen and trade-off mapping quality for reduced compilation time with a heuristic engine inspired by `PathSeeker` [10]. This engine requires the target CGRA be converted into an MRRG, which captures its resources and their connections in time, modulo some target Initiation Interval (II). Like in the hardware generation flow, this graph is constructed bottom-up, requiring only the primitives to have pre-defined structures.

Our mapping engine is generic and independent of the target CGRA architecture. It processes DFG nodes recursively in reverse topological order, i.e., working from outputs to input

nodes. In each step, it proceeds as follows: 1) all function units that are compatible with the current node and reachable from all its mapped predecessors and successors are found; 2) all routing combinations for each of these function units are computed (lazily) and tried recursively until a feasible mapping is found; 3) upon failing to place and route a node, all mapped predecessors and successors are ripped up and the algorithm tries to map the failed node before them (known as *Level 1 Recovery* [10]); and 4) upon a failed recovery, the algorithm reverts to backtracking. This procedure is repeated some times for each target II until a user-provided maximum. We map only DFGs with no backward edges, meaning accumulation requires the accumulator be stored externally and passed to the CGRA on each iteration of the DFG.

D. Automated Approximation

CGRAgen incorporates a simple automated approximation flow following successful mapping. The strategy relies on the `MarkApproximablePass` and `EstimateErrorsPass` passes to annotate the CGRA and DFG with statistic error and approximability attributes. The algorithm assigns approximation levels to DFG nodes mapped to function units with inexact arithmetic in reverse topological order using an error propagation model inspired by X-CGRA [1]. First, the error sensitivity of each approximable node is estimated by “executing” the DFG for uniform random inputs and introducing errors in one node at a time. Next, these sensitivities are used to scale error variances from inexact arithmetic applied in the DFG and validate that their sum does not exceed the user-specified constraints. We build all possible mappings with approximations and prioritize them by their number of approximated nodes and sum of approximation mode indices to maximize the potential benefits. Like the mapping engine, this approximation flow is independent of the target CGRA.

IV. EXPERIMENTING WITH CGRAGEN

To demonstrate the CGRAgen flow, we explore the architectural impact of our proposed inexact arithmetic units on CGRAs inspired by the recent literature. Following this, we carry out an illustrative experiment, involving the mapping and approximation of a Finite Impulse Response (FIR) kernel.

A. CGRA Architecture Exploration

We first consider CGRAs with PEs extracted from ADRES [11], CMA [12], and RF-CGRA [8]. The PEs differ in interconnect and pipelining and are adapted with additional registers to avoid combinational loops. For comparability, all designs are evaluated at data bit widths of 16 and 32 and integrate purely combinational ALUs that support addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, bit shifts, and common bit-wise operators. Moreover, all PEs include a 16-bit constant unit, whose output is sign-extended to 32 bits when relevant. All designs are assigned the parallel-load configuration style.

We integrate and connect the PEs into homogeneous 4×4 CGRAs and wrap the resulting architectures in shift registers, whose costs we exclude in our evaluation, to avoid over-subscribing FPGA IO pins and estimate maximum clock

TABLE I: Resource consumption and maximum frequency for select 4×4 CGRAs with and without inexact arithmetic.

Width [bits]	PE	Without AxC			With AxC		
		Area		Freq.	Area		Freq.
		# LUTs	# FFs	[MHz]	# LUTs (change)	# FFs (change)	[MHz] (change)
16	ADRES	10430	1808	62.5	11353 (+8.85%)	1840 (+1.77%)	62.5 ($\pm 0.00\%$)
	CMA	14896	2528	62.5	15328 (+2.90%)	2565 (+1.46%)	62.5 ($\pm 0.00\%$)
	RF-CGRA	14288	3569	60.6	15407 (+7.83%)	3597 (+0.78%)	61.5 (+1.54%)
32	ADRES	35711	3115	26.1	38646 (+8.22%)	3140 (+0.80%)	26.1 ($\pm 0.00\%$)
	CMA	41397	4617	25.6	44323 (+7.07%)	4626 (+0.19%)	26.1 (+1.96%)
	RF-CGRA	41098	6384	26.1	44468 (+8.20%)	6435 (+0.80%)	26.1 ($\pm 0.00\%$)
Average		26303	3670	43.9	28254 (+7.42%)	3701 (+0.83%)	44.2 (+0.54%)
Median		25304	3342	43.4	27027 (+6.81%)	3369 (+0.79%)	43.8 (+1.07%)

Fig. 2: Illustration of the CGRAgen workflow for our FIR filter kernel experiment.

frequency (up to 250 MHz in increments of 250 ps). We use AMD Vivado 2023.2 for synthesis and implementation, targeting a Zynq UltraScale+ xck26-sfvc784-2LV-c FPGA with default settings, except the `max_dsp` attribute, which we set to zero for fair comparisons given that the inexact multiplier does not map to DSP slices. This lets us measure area as Lookup Table (LUT) and Flip-Flop (FF) utilization.

The results of our experiment are listed in Table I. They indicate the different design decisions between the PEs: the ADRES-like CGRA is the simplest and consumes the fewest resources, whereas the CMA- and RF-CGRA-like architectures incur significant costs from their additional routing hardware. The architectures achieve similar clock frequencies at each bit-width. Insufficient pipelining impairs the larger designs; the designs utilize on average 7 LUTs per FF, while the FPGA fabric implements two FFs per LUT. A more balanced distribution would likely improve performance.

We also see the effects of integrating two of our proposed adders and one multiplier configured as described in Section II-D in each PE. On average, this leads to 7.42% LUT utilization overheads, negligible impact on FF utilization overheads, and, importantly, no negative influence on the maximum clock frequency. The CMA-like architecture seems more capable of absorbing part of the added LUTs than the other CGRAs. We attribute this to its two-input multiplexer logic, which cannot saturate the FPGA's LUTs.

B. Automated Kernel Approximation

We now explore the power impact of approximating a five-pin weighted average filter kernel, given in Eq. 1, to

meet different constraints, and mapping it to the RF-CGRA-like architecture from above [8]. Since this CGRA offers no concept of delaying input values from one invocation of the DFG to the next, the graph is unrolled and must have five inputs supplied in each iteration. The resulting DFG comprises five input nodes, six constants, three multiplications, three right shifts, four additions, and one output node, as the multiplications by $\delta_0 = \delta_4 = \frac{1}{2}$ are replaced by right shifts by one position. This leaves seven approximable nodes.

$$\delta_0 = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \delta_1 = 2, \quad \delta_2 = 3, \quad \delta_3 = 2, \quad \text{and} \quad \delta_4 = \frac{1}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$y_n = \frac{\delta_0 x_n + \delta_1 x_{n-1} + \delta_2 x_{n-2} + \delta_3 x_{n-3} + \delta_4 x_{n-4}}{8}$$

We conduct this experiment following the flowchart in Fig. 2, where boxes with dotted outlines represent optional steps of CGRAgen. In step ①, the CGRA and the DFG are described in their respective languages. Next, they are processed into a hardware description and a bit stream with CGRAgen in step ② by issuing the following command, assuming the directory structure of the GitHub repository:

```
$ sbt 'runMain cgragen.CGRAgen
-infer-io -gen-hw -approx-arith
src/test/resources/archparse/rf-cgra.xml
src/test/resources/dfgparse/fir.dot'
```

When completed, the generated files, `rf-cgra.v` and `rf-cgra_fir.bit`, are included in a project in AMD Vivado 2023.2 in step ③. The project is set up for out-of-context synthesis and implementation of four identical CGRAs at their maximum clock frequency of 26.1 MHz on a Zynq UltraScale+ xczu7ev-ffvc1156-2LV-e FPGA. In step ④, we simulate the implemented design for 1000 random input

Fig. 3: Power consumption of the FIR, 2nd-order polynomial, and 2×2 convolution kernels at different error constraints.

combinations and record its switching activity. The resulting file, `rf-cgra.saif`, is transformed into a power report. We repeat this process for several output error constraints that result in different approximation configurations when specified on the output node, y_n , and illustrate the dynamic power results per CGRA in Fig. 3. To build confidence in our experiment, the plot also includes results for two additional kernels: a 2nd-order polynomial, and a 2×2 convolution.

The plot shows the power consumption decreasing as the DFG is approximated. The CGRA with inexact arithmetic running the FIR kernel has a small power overhead of 2.82% over the fully exact baseline when all approximation modes are set to zero. We attribute this to the hardware overheads of our proposed arithmetic units. However, despite these overheads, the CGRA achieves 14.9% power savings when the FIR kernel is approximated maximally. Considering all three kernels, the average power overhead at no approximation shrinks to 1.92%, whereas the average savings at maximum approximation grow to 17.3%. These results are similar, albeit slightly lower, than the 22% power reduction reported for a quality-scalable PEs synthesized for an open source 15nm Application-Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) process in [1].

We duplicate the CGRA to gain measurement resolution, as Vivado 2023.2 reports power at milliwatt-level precision. We assume that the seemingly diminishing returns from the approximation and slightly lower savings than in the related work in part stem from this setup. We expect that repeating our experiments with an ASIC flow would give clearer results.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced the open source CGRagen flow for modeling and mapping application kernels to generic CGRAs with AxC features. Through example experiments, we have illustrated its usefulness in architectural design space exploration, and automated approximation. These experiments revealed 7.42% average area overheads from integrating our proposed adaptive inexact arithmetic units. They may give rise to up to 14.9% power savings when executing a FIR filter kernel in a recent CGRA.

CGRagen is the only CGRA flow with adaptive AxC and should maintain this position as it evolves. Therefore, we plan to extend it with additional approximation features, including other arithmetic units [1] and DFG alterations. Further, we plan to improve mapping speed, stability, and quality with alternative algorithms and recovery strategies. With these extensions, we will explore the differences in benefits between FPGA and ASIC implementations through additional experiments. We hope that CGRagen will spark further research into coarse-grained reconfigurable hardware and that the research community will contribute ideas and invest efforts into its development.

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VI. BIOGRAPHIES

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